

Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche
Association of European Research Libraries

LIBER is engaging with rights and values for libraries in an evolving society and academic world.

LIBER Europe (<https://libereurope.eu/>) is the voice of Europe's research library community. LIBER Europe publishes a statement on Rights & Values related to its 2023-2027 Strategy, along with a collection of deliverables from its Rights and Values Taskforce : a survey analysis and findings, a list of references with major texts useful for everyone, a poster presented at the LIBER 2026 annual conference in Trondheim, Norway. <https://zenodo.org/records/7696568>

This statement demonstrates how European research libraries are serving the common good, strengthening democracy, and benefiting librarians, researchers and citizens.

LIBER's Mission is to enable quality research guided by academic values. These are currently facing growing challenges and can no longer be taken for granted. In order to address this, LIBER, guided by values of collaboration and inclusivity, identifies three strategic priorities where academic libraries should act as key agents of trust and progress in the European research landscape:

- European solidarity and mutual respect as a fundamental principle;
- A strong commitment to make academic values known and respected;
- Enhance and promote integrity and transparency in academic library practices.

LIBER focuses on reinforcing research libraries as essential actors in safeguarding and advancing European academic values through their work with researchers, scientific communities, and data infrastructures, and in empowering libraries themselves to act in accordance with these values.

Research libraries are not just enablers of research - they can be actors themselves, committed to upholding academic values, including integrity and transparency. LIBER empowers libraries to take meaningful action to:

- Advocate for integrity and transparency in research policies and practices;
- Reinforce public trust in academic and research libraries;
- Increase solidarity across borders through collaboration and aligned principles;
- Contribute to European conversations on academic values.

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